

PROSODY AS A SUPERSEGMENTAL PHONOLOGICAL PHENOMENON IN THE
CONTEXT OF MODERN LINGUISTIC RESEARCH (BY THE EXAMPLE OF THE
CHINESE LANGUAGE)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7334237>

Nurmukhamedova Mukaddas Abdufattoh qizi
the teacher of the Uzbek state world languages university
mukaddasnur@gmail.com

Аннотация: В данной статье подробно описывается роль суперсегментных просодических элементов в китайском языке, а также на примерах сравнивается их роль в фонетике флективных и агглютинативных языков. Кроме того, с помощью примеров отражено понятие тона в китайском языке, а также явление ударения в русском и узбекском языках. Эти примеры представлены как основной источник для понимания фонетики языка.

Abstract: This article describes in detail the role of super-segmental prosodic elements in the Chinese language, and also compares their role in the phonetics of inflectional and agglutinative languages using examples. In addition, with the help of examples, the concept of tone in Chinese is reflected, as well as the phenomenon of stress in Russian and Uzbek. These examples are presented as the main source in understanding the phonetics of the language.

Ключевые слова: просодия, фонетические единицы, тон, тонема, ударение, интонация, сингармонизм, инициаль, финаль, субфиналь, сингармонирующие средства, модификация тона.

The Chinese language, unlike other language families, is distinguished by the presence of a system of tones in its composition. It is also built on syllables, i.e. one word can consist of one or more syllables, and each syllable of the whole word, in turn, is characterized by one or another tone. In the field of prosodic dominants in the Chinese language, we came to the conclusion that the phonovariants of Chinese words should be understood as a phenomenon of homonymy.

As you know, any speech activity is accompanied by the phonetic features of a particular language. In linguistics, such a branch of science as phonetics is engaged in the study of phonetic units and their features. Phonetics (from the Greek Phone - sound, voice) is a branch of linguistics that studies the sound side of speech communication, the ways in which speech sounds are formed, their changes in the speech stream, their role and the functioning of language as a means of human communication. [1.7.]

Sounding speech is the main type of speech communication, is an integral part of the functioning of the modern language and a feature of verbal languages. For the oral expression of thoughts, a person uses a special system of signs known as sounds, letters, morphemes, syllables, words and sentences.

The role of the sign is to represent, in the process of communication, any object, phenomenon or action with the help of sign units that help the word act as a substitute for the object in the human mind. So, for example, when pronouncing a particular lexeme in the mind of a person, an image of the called object is formed, for example, *хлеб, банан, яблоко, рыба*, whereas when the pronunciation is distorted, a person finds it difficult to understand, for example, *сббака, позволите= позвоните*. [2.9]

In addition to the basic phonetic units, there are segmental and supersegmental units of speech in the sound system of the language. Segment units are speech sounds that are arranged in a speech stream one after another in a linear sequence.

In the flow of speech, supersegment units cannot function separately from segment ones, i.e. they are directly interconnected and are realized only in sound combinations, superimposed on sounds and forming the structure of speech segments.

All sound units are considered in phonetics both from the point of view of reproduction and perception. Based on this, phonetics studies not only how sounding speech is formed, but also how it is perceived.

These processes are interconnected, i.e. they do not exist without each other. When a person hears speech, he articulates with himself, “pronounces” sounds. At the same time, a person cannot correctly reproduce sounds that he does not hear, for example, the English sound “th”, he hesitates about how to correctly reproduce this sound, like “s”, “f” or like “t”, or, for example, the sounds “j, q, x” in Chinese. [3.15-16.]

These aspects are important for the formation of speech skills when teaching a non-native language. In agglutinative and inflectional languages (e.g. Uzbek and Russian), words and morphemes consist of phonemes, i.e. from the sounds of the language, endowed with a meaningful function. The phonemes of each language form a certain system, according to which they are all opposed to each other. Speakers of a given language distinguish (by ear) different words or different forms of the same word, because they are different (to one degree or another) in their phonemic composition.

Usually, in the phonetic systems of many modern languages, the minimum phonetic unit is sound. The sound as the shortest unit corresponds to the abstract linguistic concept of the phoneme, which is the central concept of phonology. Sounds in the process of speech are not used in isolation, but in close connection with other sounds, forming together with them sound complexes or segments (parts) of different volume, characteristics and purpose.

The next important phonetic unit after sound is the syllable - a special sound unit formed either by one sound or by a combination of several sounds. A syllable is the smallest pronunciation unit. Even at the slowest pace of speech, we can speak in syllables rather than sounds. This is what reading is about. Syllables are the constituent elements of a more complex phonetic unit, that is, a phonetic word. A phonetic word is several syllables united by one verbal stress.

Today, the study of prosodic dominants is an important linguistic object. This is explained by the fact that supersegment units cannot exist in isolation, but function as part of segment units. The inseparability of supersegment units from segment units is the main reason for their study. Since the Chinese, Russian, Uzbek languages, as the objects of study of this dissertation research work, are languages of different systems, therefore, the prosodic dominants are different. The phonetic integrity of a word in different system languages is expressed by various means: stress, vowel harmonism, tone.

The most important distinguishing feature of the Chinese language is the presence of a tonic system and a large number of homonymous characters.

Homonyms (同音词 *tóngyīncí*) are words that sound the same but have different meanings. At the same time, the same sound in Chinese means not only the same phonetic composition, but also the same etymological tone.

Another feature of the Chinese etymological tone is its displacement, i.e. sandhi. Tone sandhi is one of the features of tonal languages, expressed in the modification of tone characteristics in combination with other tones. In Chinese, such a situation occurs when a certain sequence of tones for some reason becomes “uncomfortable” for pronunciation and, at the same time, the

melody of one or several syllables changes somewhat. In Chinese, according to its classification of syllables, there is a partial and complete change in tone.

1) Modulation of the 3rd tone in combinations of two syllables.

In cases where both tones of a syllable are pronounced with two identical 3rd tones, the 3rd tone on the first syllable changes to the 2nd. For example:

- 你好 [ní hǎo] - (how are you)

2) Modulation of the 3rd tone in three-syllable combinations.

In cases of a combination of three 3rd tones, syllables connected by semantic proximity are modulated. For example:

- 买水果 [mǎi shuǐ guǒ] - (buy fruit)

3) Semi-third (incomplete third) tone

If after the syllable pronounced by the 3rd tone, any other syllable is immediately pronounced without a pause, then the third tone changes to a half-third. For example:

- 我妈妈 [wǒ māma] - (my mother)

4) Changing the tone of the character 不 (bù)

The negative particle 不 is pronounced on the 4th tone, but if this negative particle is followed by a syllable that is also pronounced on the 4th tone, the tone 不 changes to the 2nd tone. For example:

- 不是 [bù shì] - (is not)

When observing the sandhi of tones, the meaning of phrases and sentences does not change, but differs by context. Thus, in Chinese, as in other isolating languages, syllabic tone plays an important role. Tone is the phonological unit that distinguishes syllogomorphemes.

REFERENCES

1. Knyazev, Pozharitskaya, 2003, p.-7.
2. Nurmukhamedova M.A. Comparative studies of prosodic dominant means in Chinese, Russian and Uzbek: Mag. diss. - Tashkent. 2018. - 98 p.
3. Speshnev N. A. Phonetics of the Chinese language - L., 1985. - S. 15–16.
4. Rakhmatullaeva, D., Badalbayev, D. (2022). CHINESE PHONETIC PRONUNCIATION OF UZBEK STUDENTS AN ITS TEACHING. ASEAN Journal on Science & Technology for Development: 39 pp. 393-399 (4).
5. Рахматуллаева, Д. М. (2021). 浅谈汉语声调教学问题. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(Special Issue 1), 344-348.
6. Khalmurzaeva, N. T., Omonov, Q. S., Rikhsieva, G. S., & Mirzakhmedova, K. V. (2021). SPECIFICITY OF THE ACTION OF SILENCE IN JAPANESE COMMUNICATION CULTURE. *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES* (2767-3758), 2(08), 50-55.
7. Насирова, С. А. (2019). Языковая политика в Китае: идентификация общественно-политической терминологии. In *Китайская лингвистика и синология* (pp. 384-387).
8. Хашимова, С. А. (2020). Особенности образования неодушевлённых существительных при помощи суффиксации в современном китайском языке. *Modern Oriental Studies*, 2(2), 34-46.
9. AMANOV, K. (2015). TÜRKÇE RESMİ YAZI DİLİ TARİHİNİN FASILALARA AYRILMASI. *Electronic Turkish Studies*, 10(12).
10. Халмурзаева, Н. Т. (2016). Имплицитная форма вежливости в Японской лингвокультуре: способы выражения. *European Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, (4), 19-22.
11. Nasirova, S. A. (2019). Modification of semantics of social terms of the modern Chinese language. *Opción: Revista de Ciencias Humanas y Sociales*, (24), 260-273.

12. Хашимова, С. А. (2022). АГГЛЮТИНАТИВНАЯ ОСОБЕННОСТЬ СУФФИКСАЦИИ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ КИТАЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(1), 196-202.
13. Рихсиева, Г. Ш. (2014). ОЛИЙ ТАЪЛИМ МУАССАСАЛАРИ РЕЙТИНГИ–СИФАТ ВА ТАРАҚИЁТ ОМИЛИ. *Oliy ta'lim taraqqiyoti istiqbollari= Perspectives of higher education development= Перспективы развития высшего образования: То 'plam № 2/ma'sul muharrir MA Rahmatullayev.–Издательство: Vita Color T.: 2014.–161 b, 29.*
14. Mirzakhmedova, K. V. (2021). Comparative Analysis of General Words-Terms In Persian and Uzbek Languages. *Psychology and Education Journal*, 58(1), 1050-1056.
15. Хашимова, С. А. (2022). ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ ЧИСЛИТЕЛЬНЫХ ПРИ ПОМОЩИ АФФИКСАЦИИ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ КИТАЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ. *World scientific research journal*, 7(1), 20-23.
16. Хашимова, С. А. (2020). Особенности образования неодушевлённых существительных при помощи суффиксации в современном китайском языке. *Modern Oriental Studies*, 2(2), 34-46.
17. Khalmurzaeva, N. T. (2021). Stereotypical Questions In The Organization Of The Process Of Teaching Children By Japanese Mothers. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 3(05), 513-520.